

Actinodaphne Fat as a Parent Material for a New Detergent. A Note.

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In our paper on the fat and oil from the seeds of *Actinodaphne hookeri*, Meissn (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 395) it was pointed out that the fat could be employed as a source of lauric acid. Recent work on new detergents (Duncan, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1934, 26, 24) has shown that the alkali salts of lauryl sulphate possess certain properties which from the point of view as detergents are superior to those possessed by the ordinary soap. For instance, the amount of sodium lauryl sulphate required for washing is practically independent of the hardness of water, whereas the amount of the ordinary soap required to do the same work increases rapidly with the hardness. This is because its calcium and magnesium salts, unlike the calcium and magnesium salts of the fatty acids of high molecular weight, are themselves good sudsents and good detergents. Furthermore, sodium lauryl sulphate is not easily affected by salt as the ordinary soaps are and performs as well in sea water as in tap water. The solubility and the sudsing capacity of sodium lauryl sulphate is more affected by temperature than that of the soap of corresponding molecular weight. It is, however, sufficiently soluble to sud, well in ice-cold water.

Sodium lauryl sulphate is being sold in the U. S. A. as 'Gardinol W. A.' in the textile trade and as 'Orvus' in other bulk supplies; and these developments in the field of soap chemistry have met with considerable trade acceptance. It has further found use as 'spirit cleaner' in which case a small amount of the sodium lauryl sulphate is dissolved in hydroalcoholic mixture containing about 35% alcohol and 5% glycerine.

For the preparation of the sodium lauryl sulphate, lauryl alcohol has hitherto been obtained by hydrogenation of either the cocoanut or the palm kernel oil followed by fractional distillation. The kernel fat of *Actinodaphne hookeri* which contains 96% of trilaurin can, we suggest, be used more suitably for the purpose and in this note we, therefore, record the preparation and yields of trilaurin, methyl laurate and lauryl alcohol compounds which have now acquired considerable commercial significance.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Trilaurin.—1 Kilo. of the kernels of *Actinodaphne hookeri* seeds was crushed and expressed at about 40° in a hydraulic press, yielding 480 g. (48%) of a pale yellow oil which on cooling became hard and crystalline. The residual cake on being extracted with petroleum ether further gave 270 g. of the oil, making a total yield of 750 g. (75%).

200 G. of the fat were dissolved in 2 litres of 95% hot alcohol and the contents of the flask shaken during cooling, thus preventing the separation of trilaurin as an oily product. Trilaurin crystallised out in snow-white needles which on removal and drying weighed 170-180 g. (85-90% yield).

Methyl laurate.—In 200 g. of the fat in 2 litres of methyl alcohol dry hydrogen chloride was passed upto 3%, after which the alcohol was distilled off. The residual esters were washed with sodium carbonate (2.5%) and then with water and the dried esters were submitted to fractional distillation at 5 mm. The fraction boiling at 127-130° is methyl laurate which is obtained in a yield of 90-95% (173-182 g.).

Lauryl alcohol was obtained by the modified method of Ford and Marvel ("Organic Syntheses," Vol. X, p. 62) the yield being 65-75% of the theoretical amount.

Sodium lauryl sulphate could be prepared by treating the lauryl alcohol with concentrated sulphuric acid in presence of acetic anhydride with or without a catalyst (*Deuts. Hydrierwerke A.-G.*, B. P. 307, 709; *H. T. Böhme A.-G.*, B. P. 317,039).

For commercial purposes the alcohol could easily be obtained by the high pressure hydrogenation (Schrauth, Schenck and Stickdorn, *Ber.*, 1931, **64B**, 1314) of trilaurin from *Actinodaphne* fat and from the similarly constituted fats *Litsaea* species (N. O. Laurinaceae) over sixty varieties of which are known to be found all over the country and which could serve as an easy and a cheap source of the raw material. *Litsaea sebifera* fat, for instance, contains 96% trilaurin (Schroeder, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1905, **243**, 631) and *Litsaea zeylanica* contains 85% (unpublished results by the authors). The fats from other Indian *Litsaeas* are under investigation.